

Theme 1: 'Researcher Career Stage'

The field work conducted identified that many felt that the 'career stage' of the researcher being assessed should be taken into consideration during the assessment process.

However, in order to do so, we need to have a concrete understanding of how, and according to what, researchers can be categorized in to early, mid and late career stages.

We also need to understand how we can objectively and fairly set the different expectations for early, mid and late career stages and where the 'career stage' of the researcher needs to be considered.

Question 1: How do you think the different researcher career stages could be **objectively** defined (example years active in field, years since PhD graduation, amount of produced research etc)?

- Early Career Researchers
- Mid-Career Researchers
- Late-Career Researchers

Question 2: In which of the criteria does the impact of 'researcher career stage' need to be considered?

Question 3: In relation to the criteria, you have chosen in question 2. How would you set the expectations for each career stage?

Theme 2: ‘Researcher Role in Research Publications, Development Projects and Funding Applications.’

The conducted field work identified that many felt that during the assessment process it was important for the researcher, who was being assessed, to highlight their ‘role’ in the publications, projects and funding applications they have participated in.

However, it remains unclear how the ‘role’ of the researcher in these criteria should impact the overall result of the assessment.

It is important to understand how and to what extent the highlighted ‘role’ impacts the overall outcome of the assessment of published research, conducted projects and funding applications.

Question 1: How does the ‘role’ of the researcher impact the overall assessment of research publications, development projects and funding applications?

Question 2: In each of these three criteria, to what extent is ‘role variance’ important?

Question 3: In each of these three criteria, to what extent is a ‘leading role’ important?

Theme 3: ‘Utilizing Self-Assessment and Self-Reflection.’

The field work conducted identified that many felt that the utilization of ‘self-assessment’ or ‘self-reflection’ would be very useful in the researcher assessment process.

However, the effective and objective utilization of this tool remains unclear.

It is important to identify in which criteria ‘self-assessment’ or ‘self-reflection’ could be used and how do we support its ethical, responsible and objective use.

Question 1: Which criteria can be assessed using ‘self-assessment or self-reflection’?

Question 2: What methods or precautions should be considered in the use of ‘self-assessment or self-reflection’ to help increase objectivity?

Question 3: To what extent do you think ‘self-assessment or self-reflection’ can support responsible, ethical and fair evaluation?